

Isolation of one-electron reduced product of $[\text{OsL}_3]^{2+}$ [$\text{L} = 2\text{-(arylazo)pyridines}$]

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The preparation of $[\text{OsL}_3]\text{ClO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ [$\text{L} = 2\text{-(phenylazo)pyridine (L}^1\text{)}, 2\text{-(}m\text{-tolylazo)pyridine (L}^2\text{)} \text{ and } 2\text{-(}p\text{-tolylazo)pyridine (L}^3\text{)}$] via chemical/electrochemical reduction of $[\text{OsL}_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ is described. The paramagnetic compounds display a highly intense symmetric and sharp signal with g value very close to 2.0. Results are in line with a ligand localized radical anion formation.

2-(Arylazo)pyridines (L) are non-innocent¹ N,N -chelating ligands which have seminal role in stabilizing low oxidation states of transition metals. Osmium has substantive stabilizing +2 state: dihalobis² OsX_2L_2 ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}$ or Br), tris³ $[\text{OsL}_3]^{2+}$ and mixed-tris³⁻⁵ $[\text{OsL}_2\text{D}]^{(2-z)+}$ [$\text{D} =$ neutral or anionic (N,N), (N,O) or (O,O) donors and $\text{Z} = 0-2$] complexes are afforded. cursory report on electrochemical electron transfer involving both metal oxidation and ligand reduction has been made. An ESR study of one-electron oxidized product of OsX_2L_2 revealed the electron transfer from the metal orbital⁶. However, such definitive study with the reduced product(s) has not been carried out. In the present work, we examine this point with $[\text{OsL}_3]^{2+}$. The tris-complexes of L are ideal candidates to elucidate such a problem as the first reduction (E^0 , ~ 0.1 V) is on the positive side of SCE. Although the corresponding 2,2'-bipyridine (bpy) complex $[\text{Os}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$ has first reduction⁷ at much more (E^0 , ~ 1.0 V) negative potential, the ESR study of one-electron reduced product (and the other successive one-electron reduction products) is found in literature and involvement of electron transfer to diimine ($-\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{N}=\text{C}-$) function⁸ was proposed. In this background, systematic study on the reduced product(s) of $[\text{OsL}_3]^{2+}$ in which L contains azoimine ($-\text{N}=\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{N}-$) function, deserves special attention. Herein we report the isolation and characterization of the one-electron reduced product, $[\text{OsL}_3]^+$, with special emphasis on the nature of redox orbital involved in such electron transfer.

Results and Discussion

In MeCN, $[\text{OsL}_3]^+$ is sufficiently stable to be obtained by preparative scale electrolysis at a potential 100 mV negative of the first cathodic peak. The starting osmium(II) complex $[\text{OsL}_3]^{2+}$ is regenerated quantitatively upon reoxidation

at a potential 100 mV positive to the corresponding anodic peak. In both cases, coulometry indicates the exchange of one-electron per formula unit. The original is red and in reduced form a brown colour is observed. Chemical reduction of $[\text{OsL}_3]^{2+}$ with hydrazine hydrate affords $[\text{OsL}_3]^+$, isolated as crystalline perchlorate monohydrates.

$\text{R} = \text{H}$, L^1

$\text{R} = m\text{-Me}$, L^2

$\text{R} = p\text{-Me}$, L^3

Analytical data of all the complexes are consistent with the calculated values. Some characterization data of these three complexes are given in Table 1. The air-stable moisture-insensitive complexes are highly soluble in a range of common organic solvents, such as dichloromethane, acetonitrile, methanol, ethanol but are moderately soluble in water. In acetonitrile solutions they show⁹ the expected 1 : 1 electrolytic behavior as indicated by the Λ_M values ($120-130 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$). All the complexes display characteristic ionic perchlorate bands at ~ 1100 (ν_3) and 620 (ν_2) cm^{-1} , ~ 1590 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) and ~ 1290 cm^{-1} (azo mode). A large shift (~ 140 cm^{-1}) toward lower energy than the free ligand value (1425 cm^{-1}) is indicative¹⁰ of strong π -bonding of osmium through an azo nitrogen. All other characteristic L vibrations are present in the $1600-600$ cm^{-1} range. Room-temperature solid-phase magnetic susceptibility measurements show that the complexes are uniformly paramagnetic and have moments (1.78–1.81 B.M.) close to the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M. Electronic spectra of the brown complexes show characteristic band position at ~ 480 nm with a shoulder at lower energy position.

The electroactivity of the complexes was examined in MeCN solutions using voltammetry (CV and DPV) and coulometry at platinum and glassy carbon working electrodes. The DPV technique is particularly useful for observing responses close to solvent cut-off regions. Essentially the same voltammogram (CV and DPV) is observable irrespective of whether the bulk solutions contain $[\text{OsL}_3]^+$ or $[\text{OsL}_3]^{2+}$. The results are summarized in Table 1. Three successive reversible (peak-to-peak separation, ΔE_p , 60mV) one-electron reductions are seen in CV. A fourth response overlying the solvent cutoff is observable by careful DPV experiments using dry solvent. Because of this overlap it is not clear whether the last response involves one electron or two electrons. Two oxidative couples are observable on the positive side of SCE corresponding to $[\text{OsL}_3]^+ \rightarrow [\text{OsL}_3]^{2+}$ and $[\text{OsL}_3]^{2+} \rightarrow [\text{OsL}_3]^{3+}$ transformations. The first one is close to 0.1 V and reversible (peak-to-peak separation, Δ_p , 60 mV) in CV that shows to be ideal for coulometry experiments followed by EPR study.

Two series of ESR experiments on $[\text{OsL}_3]^+$ was carried out, the one at room temperature and the other at low temperature. ESR spectra of the brown product in MeCN solutions ($1 \times 10^{-5}M$) at room temperature (25°) and MeCN-PhMe glass (-196°) show highly intense symmetric and sharp signals with g values very close to 2.0. However, line-width decreases upon lowering the temperature ($A \approx 20$ and 15 G at 25° and -196° , respectively). Doping of paramagnetic $[\text{OsL}_3]^+$ (1%) in the diamagnetic $[\text{OsL}_3]^{2+}$ as host lattice did not improve the nature of the spectrum (Fig. 1). The

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Fig. 1. X-Band ESR spectra of $[\text{OsL}_3]^{2+}$ doped in $[\text{OsL}_3]^{2+}$: (a) in MeCN at 25° and (b) in MeCN-PhMe glass at -196° .

Table 1. Some characterisation data for $[\text{OsL}_3]\text{ClO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($L = L^1-L^3$) complexes

Parameter	L^1	L^2	L^3
IR spectra (cm^{-1}) :			
$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	1592	1590	1592
$\nu_{\text{N=N}}$	1292	1290	1292
ν_{ClO_4}	1085, 620	1087, 622	1088, 620
Electronic spectra :			
λ , nm ($\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$, dm^3 $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	584 ^a (3.5), 480 (6.18), 365 ^a (11.83), 314 (14.07)	582 ^a (3.59), 479 (6.33), 363 ^a (11.89), 313 (14.16)	582 ^a (3.61), 478 (6.34), 362 ^a (11.92), 310 (14.28)
ESR data ^b :			
g (A, G)	2.006 (20) ^c 2.006 (14) ^d	2.005 (21) ^c 2.005 (15) ^d	2.005 (21) ^c 2.005 (14) ^d
Electrochemical data ^e :			
E^0 , V (ΔE_p , mV)			
Oxidative	0.10 ^{f,g} (60), 1.85 (100) -0.24 (60), -0.88 (60),	0.11 ^{f,h} (60), 1.87 (100) -0.26 (60), -0.91 (60),	0.11 ^{f,i} (60), 1.88 (100) -0.27 (60), -0.92 (60),
Reductive	-1.40 (60), -2.01 ⁱ	-1.41 (60), -2.07 ⁱ	-1.44 (60), -2.06 ⁱ

^aShoulder. ^bDoped in $[\text{OsL}_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. ^cIn MeCN solution at 25° . ^dIn MeCN-PhMe glass (-196°).

^eUnless otherwise stated, both CV and DPV data are tabulated. ^fConstant potential coulometry (oxidation done at potential $E^0 + 100$ mV) : $n = Q/Q'$, where Q' is the calculated coulomb count for one-electron transfer and Q the count found after exhaustive electrolysis of 0.01 mmol of the solute. ^g $n = 1.02$. ^h $n = 1.03$. ⁱ $n = 1.02$. ^jDPV results.

spectra of the doped polycrystalline samples change little on going from room temperature to the liquid nitrogen temperature. In MeCN solution and MeCN-PhMe glass, the magnetically dilute monocations give similar spectrum as in polycrystalline phase. With such a series of experiments where spin-exchange among individual centres are absent, the invariable observation of free electron-like ESR suggests that the unpaired electron is localized primarily on the ligand orbital rather than on the metal. The ^{14}N ($I = 1$) and ^{185}Os ($I = 3/2$; abundance, $\sim 16\%$) hyperfine lines are absent here. Under similar experimental condition, nitrogen and metal hyperfine lines are reported⁷ to be absent also in $[\text{Os}(\text{bpy})_3]^+$. To corroborate assignment of redox site in $[\text{OsL}_3]^+$, comparison of g and A values with reduced form of the free ligand was sought for, but we had not been successful in performing such experiments. This is due to the fact that coulometry passing first reduction ($E^0 \approx -1.30 \text{ V}^1$) of free L in MeCN/DMF gives continuous current which restricts ESR study of definite electroreduced species.

Now, we conclude that in $[\text{OsL}_3]^+$, a ligand localized anion $[\text{OsL}_2(\text{L}^-)]^+$ is present. A large shift of $\nu_{\text{N}=\text{N}}$ ($[\text{OsL}_3]^{2+}$, $\sim 1320 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $[\text{OsL}_3]^+$, $\sim 1290 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) stretching frequency toward lower wave number can be better accounted^{1,6} due to accumulation of free electron to π^* -orbital of azo frame rather than to metal t_2 orbital.

Experimental

A reported method¹⁰ was used to obtain the azoimine ligands (L). The preparation of $[\text{OsL}_3]^{2+}$ has been described elsewhere³. The solvents and supporting electrolyte were purified and dried by the standard procedures¹¹. All other chemicals and solvents were of A.R. grade and used as such. Solution electrical conductivity (in MeCN; solute concn. $\sim 10^{-3} \text{ M}$), microanalysis (C, H and N), magnetic susceptibility (in solid state at 25°), IR spectra (KBr), electronic spectra (MeCN) were obtained with a Philips PR 9500, a Perkin-Elmer 240 C analyzer, a PAR 155 magnetometer fitted with a Walker Scientific L 75 FBAL magnet, a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer and a Hitachi 330 spectrophotometer. EPR spectra were run on a Varian 109C E-line X-band spectrometer fitted with a quartz Dewar for measurements at -196° (liquid nitrogen); all spectra were calibrated with the help of 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl ($g = 2.0037$). Electrochemical studies were performed (in MeCN at 25°) under dry N_2 with a PAR 370-4 electrochemistry system as described elsewhere⁵. In cyclic voltammetry (CV), the following parameters and relation were used: scan rate (ν), 50 mV s^{-1} ; formal potential $E^0 = 0.5 (E_{\text{pa}} + E_{\text{pc}})$, where

E_{pa} and E_{pc} are anodic and cathodic peak potentials, respectively; ΔE_p , the peak-to-peak separation; and in differential pulse voltammetry (DPV): scan rate (ν), 10 mV s^{-1} , modulation amplitude (ΔE), 25 mV ; $E^0 = E_p + 0.5(\Delta E)$, where E_p is the DPV peak potential. The agreement between E^0 data obtained by the two techniques was good (within $\pm 5 \text{ mV}$). The potentials are referenced to a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) and are uncorrected for the junction contributions. *Caution!* Perchlorates of heavy metal ions with organic ligands are potentially explosive. The syntheses described below involve the use of perchlorate ions and isolation of the complex cations as perchlorate salts. Such a procedure may present an explosion hazard and due care should be exercised to avoid this, although we have not encountered any problem taking with small quantity of the sample.

Preparation of complexes:

The monocationic complexes were prepared from $[\text{OsL}_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ both chemically and electrochemically. The methods are described with L^2 complex.

(A) *Chemically*: Hydrazine hydrate (8 mg, 0.16 mmol) dissolved in MeCN was added dropwise to a solution of $[\text{OsL}_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (100 mg, 0.10 mmol) dissolved in the same solvent. The red colour of the solution immediately changed to brown. After stirring the mixture for 30 min it was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 ($3 \times 5 \text{ ml}$) and a crystalline solid was obtained after evaporation, which was kept *in vacuo* over P_4O_{10} to give pure $[\text{OsL}_3]^{2+}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (80 mg, 90%).

(B) *Electrochemically*: $[\text{OsL}_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (50 mg, 0.05 mmol) was reduced coulometrically at -0.22 V vs SCE in MeCN (0.1 M $[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{ClO}_4]$) until a coulomb count equivalent to one-electron transfer accumulated. During this period the colour of the solution changed from red to brown. After immediate evaporation of this solution under reduced pressure, a residue was obtained which was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 ($3 \times 5 \text{ ml}$). Evaporation followed by drying under vacuum over P_4O_{10} afforded pure $[\text{OsL}_3]^{2+}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in almost quantitative yield.

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References

1. B. K. Ghosh and A. Chakravorty, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1989, **95**, 239.
2. B. K. Ghosh, S. Goswami and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **22**, 3358; A. K. Mahapatra, B. K. Ghosh, S. Goswami and A. Chakravorty, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 101.
3. B. K. Ghosh, A. Mukhopadhyay, S. Goswami, S. Ray and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, **23**, 4633.
4. B. K. Roy, T. K. Mallick and B. K. Ghosh, *Polyhedron*, 1992, **11**, 1829; B. K. Roy, P. K. Das, T. K. Mallick and B. K. Ghosh, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1993, 154; T. K. Mallick, P. K. Das, S. Sinha and B. K. Ghosh, *Polyhedron*, 1994, **13**, 1817.
5. S. Sinha, A. K. Banerjee and B. K. Ghosh, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1997, **22**, 483; S. Sinha, A. K. Banerjee and B. K. Ghosh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 264.
6. T. K. Mallick, P. K. Das, B. K. Roy and B. K. Ghosh, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1993, **18**, 609.
7. S. Roffia, M. A. Raggi and M. Ciano, *J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.*, 1980, **108**, 69; A. A. Vlček, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1982, **43**, 39; D. J. Stufkens, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **104**, 39.
8. D. E. Morris, K. W. Hanck and M. K. DeArmond, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1985, **24**, 977.
9. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
10. R. A. Krause and K. Krause, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, **19**, 2600; 1982, **21**, 1714.
- ii. D. T. Sawyer and J. L. Roberts, Jr., "Experimental Electrochemistry for Chemists". Wiley, New York, 1974.